

First report on the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised substances in the aligned studies

Deliverable Report

D14.8

WP14 - Effect biomarkers

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1 Abstract/Summary

HBM4EU is making a great effort to describe chemical exposure to some prioritised chemical compounds, at both individual and populational levels, as well as to assess their effect on health, using new strategies and tools to enhance human exposure-effect relationships. Thus, effect biomarkers have been included as valuable indicators of the potential adverse effects exerted by environmental chemicals exposure. Further, the use of these kind of biomarkers will be of the highest value to fill existing knowledge gaps in this field.

Following the selection of both classical and novel biomarkers of effect based on extensive literature searches (D14.2, D14.3), together with the toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) information collected in WP13, WP14 has proceeded to their implementation in HBM4EU-aligned studies as well as in existing European prospective birth cohorts, once their technical validation (QA/QC) was assured. All the activities related with the implementation of biomarkers of effect have also been done in close collaboration with WP8 and WP10.

Several novel biomarkers were selected: brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and Kisspeptin (KISS54) at various levels of biological complexity. In addition, other classical biomarkers were implemented: the oxidative stress biomarker 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG), along with several reproductive and thyroid hormones, as well as some metabolic markers.

The implementation of effect biomarkers has involved the use of samples already collected (no new fieldwork was undertaken) from studies participating in the aligned studies (NIPH, NPFI, JSI, SDU, SZU, ISCI, VITO, EPIUD). Accordingly, WP14 received urine, serum, plasma and whole blood samples from some of these studies. Human biobanking samples from some European birth cohorts were also received. The followed novel effect biomarkers were finally implemented: Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) protein levels are being measured in urine and serum samples, and BDNF gene DNA methylation patterns in available whole blood samples; Kisspeptin protein (KISS54) levels in serum and plasma samples, and KISS1 gene DNA methylation patterns in available whole blood; 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) in urine samples, and the classic selected markers in serum samples.

The objective of this deliverable is to show the results of the implementation of the traditional-classical and novel effect biomarkers related to the first set of prioritised substances within the HBM4EU project. This draft shows the current status of the implementation of the effect biomarkers in the aligned studies, almost fully completed in two of the aligned studies. The delay in the results, and thus in the preparation of this deliverable, is mainly due to the consequences of the COVID pandemic in the participating laboratories. The work continues and is expected to be completed by the end of the project. At the time of submitting this deliverable, the analysis of the last samples received from the aligned studies (e.g. NIPH, Norway) is still being finalised.

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2 Introduction

Several novel biomarkers were selected: the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and Kisspeptin (KISS54) at several levels of biological complexity. Classical or “established” biomarkers were also considered; those which their responses and sensitivities have been previously documented (including in vitro, in vivo and epidemiological studies). For example, the biomarker 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG) which may provide information on damage caused by elevated levels of oxidants (i.e., oxidative stress) and also on capacities of the studied biological system to respond to oxidative stress and/or the capacity of detoxification in general. Several classic reproductive and thyroid hormones markers as well as some metabolic parameters were also included.

The selection of both classic and novel effect biomarkers (D14.2, D14.3) was based on comprehensive literature searches conducted inside WP14, and together with toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) information collected in WP13. These biomarkers were meant to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies and selected prospective European birth cohorts.

As a brief reminder, some considerations to define a valid biomarker to detect chemically-induced adverse outcomes in animals and humans are detailed as follows:

1. It should demonstrate the correlation with the response which is trying to predict (with the truth)
2. Acceptable selectivity and specificity
3. Adequate sensitivity
4. The biology and performance of the biomarker are aligned with its use:
5. Acceptable magnitude of changes in response to the environmental compound
6. Cover an appropriate measurement range
7. Acceptable intra- and inter-subject variability associated with the biomarker’s baseline and response
8. The availability of reliable and reproducible measurement methodology
9. Analytical and clinical validation should show that the biomarker is appropriated for its proposed use

According to AD8.4, WP14 received urine, serum, plasma and whole blood samples from European birth cohorts. Details regarding the distribution of measured parameters and cohorts are detailed in Tables 1 and 2 (AD8.4).

Due to the global pandemic situation of COVID-19 some of the participating laboratories have suffered several interruptions and delays in their analysis. In spite of this, WP14 is trying to have all results on time. The current status of the analyses is shown in Tables 3 and 4. Briefly, the FleSH and BEA cohorts have been fully analysed, and data regarding the new effect biomarkers serum BDNF protein, and Kisspeptin 54 protein, as well as the classical effect biomarkers have been sent to the study owners as well as to the WP10 leader. In addition, serum BDNF protein, and Kisspeptin 54 protein levels from the PCB cohort (Slovakia) and the SLO CRP cohort (Slovenia), NEB II (Norway), the INAIRQ cohort (Hungary), and the NAC II cohort (Italy), have been evaluated and sent to their respective study owners.

However, not all of the classical effect biomarkers have been finalised, namely some of the analyses of the PCB, SLO CRP and NEBII cohorts, as well as leptin and adiponectin levels, are

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still in progress. Nevertheless, all the expected classical effect biomarkers will be ready by the end of December 2021.

INSERM has also validated the measurement of BDNF and Kisspeptin DNA methylation in blood, as well as the measures for histone modifications for ER, AR, PPAR α , PPAR γ , GR and TR. They are now working in the DNA methylation analysis of the human aligned samples from HBM4EU. There was an unexpected delay in the start of these analysis due to long administrative process required to import the samples, and all the analysis will be completed by the beginning of 2022.

The original plan for OHdG analyses in urine samples from the HBM4EU aligned studies was to evaluate this marker in three European countries (SK, ESP and NO; n=300 samples each). However, it was not possible to retrieve samples from the NIPH cohort (NO), so it has only been possible to analyse samples from SK and ESP. In the samples received, MU also assessed creatinine levels. All results were provided to the owners of the corresponding studies (SZU in SK and ISCIII in ESP).

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Table 1: Overview table analysis in children conducted under WP14

Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>children</u>	MATRIX	Region	North		East		South	
		Study	NEB II	OCC	PCB COHORT	INAIHQ	SLO CRP	NAC II
		Country	NO	DK	SK	HU	SL	IT
		N° samples	300	300	300	264	148	300
		Age (years)	6-11	6-7	10-12	8-11	7-10	6-8
Clinical effect biomarkers (<i>TSH, T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG</i>)	Serum		√ ¹	√	-	-	√	-
BDNF	serum			-	-	-	√	-
BDNF	Urine		√	-	√	√	-	√
Targeted DNA methylation (<i>BDNF</i>)	Whole blood		√	-	-	-	√ ²	-
Histone modifications (<i>ER, AR, TR</i>)	Whole blood		√	-	-	-	√	-
Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.					-
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood		A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.					-

“√” = parameter will be analysed, “-” = parameter will not be analysed.

¹ NIPH: Only a subset of the clinical markers will be assessed, 7 of the 8 clinical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (7*25 µL).

² Extracted DNA will be sent for DNA methylation analysis instead of whole blood

Table 2: Overview table analysis in teenagers conducted under WP14

	Region	North	East	South		West
		Study	NEBII	PCB cohort (follow-up)	SLO CRP	BEA
Country	NO	SK	SL	ES	BE	
N samples	184	300	98	300	300	
Age (years)	12-14	15-16	12-15	14-16	14-15	
Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>teenagers</u>	MATRIX					
Clinical effect biomarkers (LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, glucose, insulin, TG, TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, leptin, adiponectin, TSH, T3, T4)	Serum	√ ³	√	√	√	√
Kisspeptin	serum	√ ⁴	√	√	√ ⁴	√
8-OHdG	Urine	√	√	√ ⁵	√	√ ⁵
Targeted DNA methylation (Kisspeptin)	Whole blood	√	-	√ ⁶	√	√
Histone modifications (ER, AR, PPARα, PPARγ, GR, TR)	Whole blood	√	-	√	√	√
Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available teenager samples.				
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.				

³ NIPH: Only a subset of the classical biomarkers will be assessed, both in children and teenagers, i.e. 7 of the classical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (8*25 uL). As part of another study the other classical biomarkers were measured and these data will be shared. Classical biomarkers and BDNF will be measured in plasma instead of serum.

⁴ ISCIII and NIPH: Kisspeptin will be analysed if sufficient sample volume available.

⁵ JSI and VITO: 8-OHdG data already available and will be shared.

⁶ Extracted DNA will be sent for DNA methylation analysis instead of whole blood

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Table 3: Current status of effect biomarkers analysis (Children)

Children						
Cohort	Country	N	matrix	biomarker	status	Analysed by
PCB	SLOVAKIA (SZU)	299	urine	BDNF	done	UGR
CRP	SLOVENIA (JSI)	148	serum	BDNF	done	UGR
				Classical biomarkers	done	
INAIHQ	HUNGARY (NPHI)	264	urine	BDNF	done	UGR
NAC II	ITALY (UNIUD)	300	urine	BDNF	done	UGR
NEBII	NORWAY (NIPH)	300	urine	BDNF	done	UGR
		294	plasma	Kisspeptin		

Table 4: Current status of effect biomarkers analysis (Teenagers)

Teenagers						
Cohort	Country	N	Matrix	Biomarker	status	Analysed by
PCB	SLOVAKIA (SZU)	289	Serum	8OH-dG	done	MU
				Kisspeptin	done	UGR
				Classical biomarkers	done	
CRP	SLOVENIA (JSI)	98	Serum	Kisspeptin	done	UGR
				Classical biomarkers	done	
NEBII	NORWAY (NIPH)	169	Plasma	Kisspeptin	done	UGR
FLESH	BELGIUM (VITO)	239	Serum	Kisspeptin	done	UGR
				BDNF	done	
				Classical biomarkers	done	
BEA	SPAIN (ISCIII)	295	Serum	8OH-dG	done	MU
				Kisspeptin	done	UGR
				BDNF	Done	
				Classical biomarkers	Done	

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3 Results

This draft deliverable shows the current status of the implementation of biomarkers of effect in the aligned studies, almost entirely completed for two of the aligned studies. The delay is mainly due to the covid pandemic. The work continues and is expected to be completed by the end of 2021.

The results of the new biomarkers implemented in all the included aligned studies are shown below, as well as the data of the classical biomarkers for the two aligned studies completed (FLESH and BEA).

3.1 Novel effect biomarkers

3.1.1 FLESH cohort (VITO)

3.1.1.1 BDNF

UGR received 239 serum samples from the FLESH cohort. After their reception, samples were defrosted, vortexed, and aliquoted into 30 and 50 µL to test BDNF and KISS54 proteins, respectively. A total of three assays were needed to measure serum BDNF levels, graphically showed in Figure 1. Mean (SD) serum BDNF were 35.0 (15.8) ng/mL, showing 0.5 ng/mL as minimum, and 108.9 ng/mL as maximum. Total inter-coefficient of variation (mean of inter-CVs from the three independent assays) was 10.04%, thus deemed positive for optimal quality (Table 5). No incidents were found while performing the assays.

Figure 1: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): FleSH cohort (VITO-Belgium); adolescent population

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Table 5: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): FleSH cohort (VITO-Belgium); adolescent population

Serum samples (n=239)		
CV (%)		10.04
Mean		35.0
SD		15.8
Min.		0.5
Max.		108.9
Percentiles	25	24.4
	50	37.2
	75	45.5

3.1.1.2 Kisspeptin

To measure kiss54 in serum, three assays were performed. No incidences were found during analyses. Concentrations of serum kiss54 are graphically shown in Figure 2. Briefly, mean (SD) levels of kiss54 were 2150 pg/mL, with minimum and maximum levels of 922.75 and 3152.83 pg/mL, respectively. Inter-CV was 7.40%, thus deemed positive for optimal quality (Table 6).

Figure 2: Serum Kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): FleSH cohort (VITO-Belgium); adolescent population

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Table 6: Serum Kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): FleSH cohort (VITO-Belgium); adolescent population

Serum samples (n=239)		
CV (%)	7.40	
Mean	2150.43	
SD	261.71	
Min.	922.75	
Max.	3152.83	
Percentiles	25	2002.75
	50	2142.83
	75	2317.83

3.1.2 BEA cohort (ISCIII)

3.1.2.1 BDNF

UGR received 295 serum samples from the BEA cohort. The samples arrived thawed, but were immediately stored at -80°C. Prior to analyses, serum samples were thawed, vortex mixed, and aliquoted into 30 and 50 µL to analyse BDNF and KISS54 protein levels, respectively. Four assays were required to measure serum BDNF levels, shown in Figure 3. No incidences were found when performing these assays. Serum BDNF levels showed a mean (SD) value of 35.74 (12.47) ng/mL, and a minimum level of 10.15 ng/mL and a maximum level of 73.85 ng/mL. The total coefficient of variation (CV) was 5.53%, indicating that the BDNF data are of optimal quality (Table 7).

Figure 3: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

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Table 7: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

Serum samples (n= 295)		
CV (%)	5.53	
Mean	35.74	
SD	12.47	
Min.	10.15	
Max.	73.85	
Percentiles	25	25.75
	50	34.50
	75	43.48

3.1.2.2 Kisspeptin

UGR received 295 serum samples from the BEA cohort. The samples arrived thawed, but were immediately stored at -80°C. Serum kiss 54 protein levels were measured without incident. A total of four assays were required to complete its measurement. Serum kiss54 concentrations are summarised in Figure 4. The mean (SD) was 2183.74 (274.78) pg/mL, with a range of maximum and minimum values of 1132.75 and 3198.75 pg/mL, respectively (Table 8). The inter-CV mean of the four independent assays was 4.40%, so the kiss54 data can be considered to be of optimal quality, as stated in D14.7.

Figure 4: Serum Kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

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Table 8: Serum Kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

Serum samples (n= 295)		
CV (%)		4.40
Mean		2183.74
SD		274.78
Min.		1132.08
Max.		3198.75
Percentiles	25	2000.88
	50	2197.92
	75	2358.75

3.1.2.3 hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG)

A total of 300 urine samples from the BEA cohort were received and analysed successfully by MU. Analyses of 8-OHdG were performed with Waters Acquity LC chromatograph (Waters, Manchester, U.K.). Concentration of 8-OHdG were corrected for the content of internal standard and expressed as microgram per litter of urine (Table 9).

Table 9: Urine 8-OHdG levels (µg/L): BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

Urine samples BEA cohort (n=300)	
Mean	5.68
Median	5.09
Min.	0.4
Max.	20.25

3.1.3 PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia)

3.1.3.1 BDNF

UGR received 299 urinary samples from PCB cohort. Samples were kept at -80°C. Four assays were needed to measure serum BDNF levels, showed in Figure 5 and 6. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Serum BDNF levels showed a mean (SD) value of 3.471 (1.003) ng/mL, with minimum levels of 0.154 ng/mL and maximum levels of 5.574. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 10.6%, indicating that BDNF data followed an optimal quality (Table 10).

Figure 5: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); children population

Figure 6: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); children population

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Table 10: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); children population

Urine samples (n= 299)		
CV (%)		10.6
Mean		3.471
SD		1.003
Min.		0.154
Max.		5.574
Percentile	25	2.963
	50	3.445
	75	3.933

3.1.3.2 Kisspeptin

UGR received 289 serum samples from PCB cohort. Samples were kept at -80°C. Serum kiss 54 was measured without incidences. A total of four assays were needed to complete its measurement. Concentrations of serum kiss54 are summarised in Figure 7. Mean (SD) kiss54 was 2288.19 (263.52) pg/mL, and ranges reporting its lowest and highest values were 1417.81 and 3093.50 pg/mL, respectively (Table 11). Mean inter-CV of the four independent assays were 5.90%, thus kiss54 data was considered as optimal quality measurements, according to D14.7.

Figure 7: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); adolescent population

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Figure 8: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); adolescent population

Table 11: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); adolescent population

Serum samples (n= 289)		
CV (%)		5.90
Mean		2288.19
SD		263.52
Min.		1417.81
Max.		3093.50
Percentiles	25	2098.78
	50	2308.50
	75	2462.09

3.1.3.3 hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG)

A total of 300 urine samples from the PCB cohort were received and analysed successfully by MU. Analyses of 8-OHdG were performed with Waters Acquity LC chromatograph (Waters, Manchester, U.K.). Concentration of 8-OHdG were corrected for the content of internal standard and expressed as microgram per litter of urine (Table 12).

Table 12: Urine 8OHdG levels µg/L: PCB cohort (SZU-Slovakia); adolescent population

Urine samples PCB cohort (n=285)	
Mean	5.3
Median	4.5
Min.	0.19
Max.	27.96

3.1.4 INAIRQ cohort (NPHI-Hungary)

UGR received 261 urine samples from INAIRQ cohort. Four assays were needed to measure urine BDNF levels, showed in Figure 9 y 10. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Urinary BDNF levels showed a mean (SD) value of 2.467 (1.016) ng/mL, showing minimum levels of <0.066 ng/mL and maximum levels of 4.582. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 12.8%, so BDNF data followed an optimal quality (Table 13).

Figure 9: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): INAIRQ cohort (NPHI-Hungary); children population

Figure 10: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): INAIRQ cohort (NPHI-Hungary); children population

Table 13: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): INAIRQ cohort (NPHI-Hungary); children population

Urine samples (n= 261)		
CV (%)		12.8
Mean		2.467
SD		1.016
Min.		<0.066
Max.		4.582
Percentile	25	2.093
	50	2.546
	75	3.060

3.1.5 NAC-II cohort (EPIUD-Italy)

UGR received 300 urine samples from NAC-II cohort. Four assays were needed to measure urine BDNF levels, showed in Figure 11 y 12. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Urinary BDNF levels showed a mean (SD) value of 2.832 (1.299) ng/mL, showing minimum levels of <0.066 ng/mL and maximum levels of 6.255. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 9.57%, so BDNF data followed an optimal quality (Table 14).

Figure 11: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): NAC-II cohort (EPIUD-Italy) children population

Figure 12: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): NAC-II cohort (EPIUD-Italy) children population

Table 14: Urinary BDNF levels (ng/mL): NAC-II cohort (EPIUD-Italy) children population

Urine samples (n= 300)		
CV (%)		9.57
Mean		2.832
SD		1.299
Min.		<0.066
Max.		6.255
Percentile	25	2.150
	50	2.815
	75	3.564

3.1.6 SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia)

3.1.6.1 BDNF

UGR received 130 serum samples from JSI cohort. Samples were kept at -80°C. Previous to analyses, serum samples were defrosted, vortexed, and aliquoted into 30 and 50 µL to test BDNF and KISS54 proteins, respectively. Four assays were needed to measure serum BDNF levels, showed in Figure 13 y 14. No incidences were found while performing the assays. Serum BDNF levels showed a mean (SD) value of 45.55 (10.14) ng/mL, showing minimum levels of 25.23 ng/mL and maximum levels of 81.33. Total inter-coefficient of variation (CV) was 4.95%, so BDNF data followed an optimal quality (Table 15).

Figure 13: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); children population

Figure 14: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); children population

Table 15: Serum BDNF levels (ng/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); children population

Serum samples (n=130)		
CV (%)	4.95	
Mean	45.55	
SD	10.14	
Min.	25.23	
Max.	81.33	
Percentiles	25	38.57
	50	44.86
	75	52.56

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3.1.6.2 Kisspeptin

Serum kiss 54 was measured without incidences. A total of four assays were needed to complete its measurement. Concentrations of serum kiss54 are summarised in Figure 15 y 16. Mean (SD) kiss54 was 2119.23 (334.25) pg/mL, and ranges reporting its lowest and highest values were 1085.00 and 2725.00 pg/mL, respectively (Table 16). Mean inter-CV of the four independent assays were 6.10%, thus kiss54 data was considered as optimal quality measurements, according to D14.7.

Figure 15: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); adolescent population

Figure 16: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); adolescent population

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Table 16: Serum kisspeptin levels (pg/mL): SLO-CRP cohort (JSI-Slovenia); adolescent population

Serum samples (n= 93)		
CV (%)		6.10
Mean		2119.23
SD		334.25
Min.		1085.00
Max.		2725.00
Percentiles	25	2001.75
	50	2223.50
	75	2328.50

3.2 Classical Biomarkers

3.2.1 FLESH cohort (VITO)

In 239 serum samples from adolescent population (FLESH Cohort) were quantified several hormone levels (FSH, E2, SHBG, FT4, FT3, TSH and Testosterone) as well as some metabolic marker levels (Insulin, Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Glucose, HDL and LDL-C). Based on the results obtained, different statistic parameters were calculated for each clinical biomarker as presented in Table 17.

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Table 17: Clinical biomarkers: FLESH cohort (VITO-Belgium); adolescent population

Hormone marker levels							
Clinicals Biomarkers	FSH (U/L)	E2 (pg/mL)	SHBG (nmol/L)	FT4 (ng/dL)	FT3 (pg/ml)	TSH (µIU/ml)	TT (ng/dL)
N	238	239	237	239	239	239	239
Average	5.2	50.9	61.9	0.8	3.5	2	145.1
Geometric Mean	4.4	33.3	51.2	0.8	3.5	1.9	82.2
P5	1.4	15	17.68	0.629	2.819	0.943	20
P95	9.6	180.4	131.4	1	4.2	3.6	478.9
Metabolic marker levels							
Clinicals Biomarkers	Insulin (mIU/mL)	Cholesterol	TG	Glucose	HDL	LDL-C	
		(mg/dL)					
N	238	239	239	239	239	239	
Average	13.5	157.9	90.9	88.4	51.9	101.9	
Geometric Mean	10	155.5	83.5	86.5	50.8	99.7	
P5	2.54	115	44.9	63	36	71	
P95	33.4	206.2	164.8	112	71	140.3	

TG= Triglycerides; TT: Total testosterone

All parameters were measured in the total of the samples (N= 239) except for one missing FSH and Insulin, and two missing SHBG. As main results, the average value for E2 and TT were respectively: 50.9 pg/mL and 145.1 ng/dL. The geometric mean was 50.8 mg/dL for HDL and 155.5 mg/dL for cholesterol.

3.2.2 BEA cohort (ISCIII)

In 295 serum samples from adolescent population (BEA Cohort) were quantified hormone marker levels (FSH, E2, SHBG, FT4, FT3, TSH and Testosterone) and metabolic marker levels (Insulin, Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Glucose, HDL and LDL-C). Based on the results obtained, different statistic parameters were calculated for each clinical biomarker as presented in the Table 18.

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Table 18: Clinical markers: BEA cohort (ISCIII-Spain); adolescent population

Hormone marker levels							
Clinicals Biomarkers	FSH (U/L)	E2 (pg/mL)	SHBG (nmol/L)	FT4 (ng/dL)	FT3 (pg/ml)	TSH (µIU/ml)	TT (ng/dL)
N	292	291	291	292	292	292	291
Average	5.2	54.9	36.7	0.9	3.7	1.7	196.2
Geometric Mean	4.7	35.5	32.6	0.9	3.6	1.6	122
P5	2	15	15.35	0.77	3	1.07	29
P95	8.8	198.2	67.7	1.1	4.2	2.6	486.2
Metabolic marker levels							
Clinicals Biomarkers	Insulin (mIU/mL)	Cholesterol	TG	Glucose	HDL	LDL	
		(mg/dL)					
N	292	293	295	295	295	295	
Average	8.6	144.8	71.6	46.6	44.7	92.5	
Geometric Mean	7.3	141.9	63.5	40.9	43	88.5	
P5	3.58	108.9	35.7	10	29.5	61	
P95	20.2	193	138.3	76	60	132	

TG= Triglycerides; TT: Total testosterone

Almost all metabolic parameters were measured in the total of the samples (N= 295) except for two missing Cholesterol levels and three missing Insulin. As main results, the average value for E2 and TT were respectively: 54.9 pg/mL and 196.2 ng/dL. The geometric mean was 43 mg/dL for HDL and 141.9 mg/dL for cholesterol.

4 Pilot studies

Within WP14, several pilot studies are also being conducted to ascertain the added value of effect biomarkers for human biomonitoring purposes. According to the planned hypothesis, effect biomarkers could be helpful to increase the causal inference in exposure-effect associations. Thus, the role of BDNF in the associations of bisphenol A (BPA), metals, and non-persistent pesticide metabolites with the behavioural function of Spanish adolescent males aged 15-17 years old, was assessed.

The existing European study population was the INMA (Environment and childhood)-Granada birth cohort. Figure 17 shows the overall associations found in all three pilot studies conducted. A summary of the obtained results across studies is also included.

Additional pilot studies within other existing European prospective cohorts are ongoing in WP14.

Figure 17: BDNF: Panel of associations observed in the pilot studies from the INMA-Granada cohort

4.1 Pilot study 1: Longitudinal study with BPA and BDNF

Because Bisphenol A (BPA) exposure has been linked to altered behaviour in children, within the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU), an adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network was constructed supporting the mechanistic link between this environmental compound and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF). The objective of this pilot study was to test this toxicologically-based hypothesis in the prospective INMA-Granada birth cohort (Spain). For that purpose, BPA concentrations were quantified by LC-MS/MS in spot urine samples from boys aged 9–11 years,

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normalised by creatinine and log-2 transformed. In adolescents (15–17 years), blood and urine specimens were collected, and serum and urinary BDNF protein levels were measured using immunoassays. DNA methylation levels at 6 CpGs in Exon IV of the BDNF gene were also assessed in peripheral blood using bisulfite pyrosequencing. Adolescent's behaviour was parent-rated using the Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL/6-18) in 148 boys. Adjusted linear regression and mediation models were fit.

Results indicated that childhood urinary BPA concentrations were longitudinally and positively associated with thought problems ($\beta=0.76$; 95%CI: 0.02, 1.49) and somatic complaints ($\beta=0.80$; 95%CI: -0.16, 1.75) at adolescence (Figure 18). BPA concentrations were positively associated with BDNF DNA methylation at CpG6 ($\beta = 0.21$; 95%CI: 0.06, 0.36) and mean CpG methylation ($\beta = 0.10$; 95%CI: 0.01, 0.18), but not with total serum or urinary BDNF protein levels.

When independent variables were categorised in tertiles, positive dose-response associations were observed between BPA-thought problems (p -trend= 0.08), BPA-CpG6 (p -trend ≤ 0.01), and CpG6-thought problems (p -trend ≤ 0.01) (Figure 18). A significant mediated effect by CpG6 DNA methylation was observed ($\beta=0.23$; 95%CI: 0.01, 0.57), accounting for up to 34% of the BPA-thought problems association (Figure 19). We concluded that, in line with toxicological studies, BPA exposure was longitudinally associated with increased BDNF DNA methylation, supporting the biological plausibility of BPA-behaviour relationships previously described in the epidemiological literature. Given its novelty and preliminary nature, this effect biomarker approach will be replicated in the HBM4EU studies.

Figure 18: Relationships among BPA exposure, CpG6 DNA methylation and thought problems categorising the independent variable in tertiles to assess dose-response trends within the most robust findings. Figure taken from Mustieles et al., (2022).

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Figure 19: Mediation model showing associations between childhood urinary BPA concentrations, BDNF DNA methylation and thought problems t-scores at adolescence (n = 103)

Beta coefficients and 95% CIs are reported for the total, direct and indirect (i.e., mediated) effects. Continuous log₂-transformed BPA concentrations and CpG6 methylation percentage, and continuous thought problems t-scores were used. Models were adjusted for age and BMI z-scores (continuous) at neuropsychological evaluation (15–17 years), maternal education (primary, secondary or university), urinary cotinine at 9–11 years (continuous), and alcohol consumption (yes/no) at adolescence. This figure was taken from Mustieles et al., (2022).

This pilot study was published in the Scientific of the Total Environment (STOTEN) journal, with the title “**BDNF as a potential mediator between childhood BPA exposure and behavioral function in adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort**” (Mustieles et al., 2022).

4.2 Pilot study 2: Cross-sectional study with metal elements and BDNF

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) plays an important role in brain development by regulating multiple pathways within the central nervous system. In the Human Biomonitoring for Europe Project (HBM4EU), this neurotrophin is being implemented as a novel effect biomarker to evaluate the potential threats of environmental chemicals on neurodevelopment. Thus, the objective of pilot study 2 was exploring the relationships among exposure to environmental metals, BDNF biomarkers at two levels of biological complexity, and behavioural function in adolescent males.

Data were gathered from 125 adolescents on: spot urine sample total concentrations of the neurotoxic metal(oid)s arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg), and lead (Pb); serum BDNF protein concentrations; and concurrent behavioural functioning according to the Child Behaviour Check List (CBCL/6–18). In 113 of the participants, information was also collected on blood BDNF DNA methylation at six CpGs. Associations were evaluated by multivariate linear regression analysis adjusted for confounders.

As, Cd, Hg, and Pb were detected in 100%, 98.5%, 97.0%, and 89.5% of urine samples, respectively. Median serum BDNF concentration was 32.6 ng/mL, and total percentage of BDNF gene methylation was 3.8%. In the adjusted models, urinary As was non-linearly associated with more internalising problems and Cd with more externalising behaviours.

The percentage BDNF DNA methylation at CPGs #5 and the mean percentage CpG methylation increased across As tertiles (p-trend = 0.04 and 0.03, respectively), while 2nd tertile and 3rd tertile of Cd concentrations were associated with lower serum BDNF and higher CpG3 methylation

percentage (Figure 20). Additionally, when BDNF was categorised in tertiles, serum BDNF at the 3rd tertile was associated with fewer behavioural problems, particularly withdrawn (p -trend = 0.04), social problems (p -trend = 0.12), and thought problems (p -trend = 0.04).

Exposure to As and Cd was associated with BDNF gene DNA methylation BDNF gene and serum BDNF, respectively. Associations with DNA methylation may be attributable to a higher variability over time in circulating BDNF concentrations than in the methylation status of this gene. Caution should be taken when interpreting the results relating postnatal Pb and Hg to behavioural functioning. Further studies are then needed to verify these findings.

	Model 1				Model 2			
	As tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)				Cd tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)			
	1st (LOD-2.29)	2nd (2.31–3.56)	3rd (3.57–6.85)	p-trend	1st (LOD-2.29)	2nd (2.31–3.56)	3rd (3.57–6.85)	p-trend
	Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)		Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
sBDNF	35.8 (10.3)	-1.60 (-6.87,3.67)	-3.60 (-9.08,1.89)	0.19	35.7 (10.6)	-0.91 (-6.43,4.62)	-3.47 (-9.13,2.18)	0.20
metBDNF								
CpG 1	4.6 (0.8)	-0.26 (-0.77,0.26)	-0.08 (-0.63,0.47)	0.86	4.6 (0.9)	-0.21 (-0.74,0.32)	-0.07 (-0.64,0.49)	0.87
CpG 2	3.1 (0.5)	0.23 (-0.09,0.55)	0.26 (-0.08,0.60)	0.15	3.09 (0.5)	0.23 (-0.10,0.55)	0.28 (-0.07,0.63)	0.13
CpG 3	3.2 (0.5)	0.24 (-0.11,0.59)	0.33 (-0.04,0.70)†	0.09	3.2 (0.5)	0.18 (-0.17,0.53)	0.27 (-0.11,0.64)	0.16
CpG 4	5.8 (0.9)	0.44 (-0.30,1.18)	0.68 (-0.11,1.46)†	0.09	5.8 (0.9)	0.38 (-0.38,1.14)	0.67 (-0.14,0.48)	0.10
CpG 5	3.1 (0.7)	0.45 (-0.04,0.94)†	0.57 (0.05,1.09)*	0.04	3.1 (0.7)	0.37 (-0.12,0.85)	0.52 (0.01,1.03)*	0.05
CpG 6	2.5 (0.9)	0.57 (-0.16,1.30)	0.72 (-0.07,1.52)†	0.07	2.5 (0.8)	0.44 (-0.27,1.15)	0.61 (-0.17,1.38)	0.13
CpG t	3.7 (0.5)	0.34 (-0.05,0.72)†	0.48 (0.07,0.89)*	0.03	3.7 (0.5)	0.28 (-0.10,0.66)	0.44 (0.04,0.84)*	0.04
	Cd tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)				Hg tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)			
	1st (LOD-0.06)	2nd (0.06–0.10)	3rd (0.11–0.34)	p-trend	1st (LOD-0.40)	2nd (0.41–0.86)	3rd (0.86–4.57)	p-trend
	Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)		Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
sBDNF	37.3 (10.1)	-6.77 (-11.59,-1.96)**	-5.03 (-10.55,0.49)†	0.07	37.3 (10.1)	-7.05 (-12.02,-2.12)**	-5.95 (-11.68,-0.23)*	0.04
metBDNF								
CpG 1	4.6 (1.0)	-0.21 (-0.71,0.29)	-0.14 (-0.72,0.43)	0.61	4.6 (1.0)	-0.25 (-0.76,0.25)	-0.18 (-0.76,0.40)	0.54
CpG 2	3.3 (0.5)	-0.03 (-0.34,0.27)	-0.22 (-0.58,0.13)	0.22	3.3 (0.5)	-0.04 (-0.35,0.27)	-0.22 (-0.58,0.14)	0.23
CpG 3	3.4 (0.6)	-0.21 (-0.55,0.12)	-0.33 (-0.71,0.06)†	0.09	3.4 (0.6)	-0.22 (-0.55,0.11)	-0.33 (-0.71,0.06)†	0.09
CpG 4	6.0 (1.1)	0.06 (-0.65,0.78)	-0.06 (-0.90,0.78)	0.89	6.0 (1.1)	0.09 (-0.63,0.82)	-0.05 (-0.90,0.80)	0.92
CpG 5	3.3 (0.8)	0.06 (-0.42,0.55)	-0.02 (-0.57,0.54)	0.95	3.3 (0.8)	0.09 (-0.38,0.56)	0.01 (-0.53,0.54)	0.98
CpG 6	2.7 (1.1)	0.19 (-0.54,0.92)	0.04 (-0.80,0.89)	0.91	2.7 (1.1)	0.25 (-0.46,0.96)	0.06 (-0.75,0.87)	0.89
CpG t	3.9 (0.6)	-0.03 (-0.39,0.33)	-0.17 (-0.60,0.26)	0.44	3.9 (0.6)	-0.04 (-0.39,0.31)	-0.19 (-0.61,0.23)	0.37
	Pb tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)				Pb tertiles ($\mu\text{g/L}$)			
	1st (LOD-0.34)	2nd (0.34–0.58)	3rd (0.59–4.45)	p-trend	1st (LOD-0.34)	2nd (0.34–0.58)	3rd (0.59–4.45)	p-trend
	Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)		Mean (SD)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
sBDNF	35.2 (9.9)	-0.35 (-5.29,4.59)	0.00 (-5.69,5.69)	0.99	35.1 (10.2)	0.23 (-4.88,5.35)	1.16 (-4.86,7.18)	0.70
metBDNF								
CpG 1	4.6 (0.9)	-0.29 (-0.75,0.17)	0.40 (-0.15,0.96)	0.24	4.6 (1.0)	-0.21 (-0.69,0.26)	0.51 (-0.08,1.10)†	0.14
CpG 2	3.2 (0.5)	0.07 (-0.22,0.36)	-0.10 (-0.46,0.25)	0.63	3.2 (0.5)	0.05 (-0.25,0.35)	-0.15 (-0.53,0.22)	0.46
CpG 3	3.3 (0.6)	-0.07 (-0.39,0.25)	-0.29 (-0.68,0.10)	0.15	3.3 (0.6)	-0.07 (-0.39,0.25)	-0.26 (-0.66,0.15)	0.22
CpG 4	5.9 (1.1)	0.26 (-0.38,0.89)	-0.58 (-1.39,0.22)	0.25	5.9 (1.1)	0.21 (-0.45,0.87)	-0.66 (-1.52,0.20)	0.21
CpG 5	3.3 (0.8)	-0.02 (-0.47,0.43)	-0.45 (-0.99,1.00)	0.13	3.2 (0.8)	-0.03 (-0.48,0.41)	-0.45 (-1.00,0.11)	0.13
CpG 6	2.7 (1.0)	-0.06 (-0.73,0.61)	-0.65 (-1.50,0.20)	0.16	2.7 (1.1)	-0.04 (-0.70,0.62)	-0.54 (-1.38,0.31)	0.24
CpG t	3.8 (0.6)	0.03 (-0.31,0.37)	-0.25 (-0.67,0.18)	0.31	3.8 (0.6)	0.03 (-0.31,0.37)	-0.25 (-0.68,0.18)	0.30

Figure 20: *Model 1*: adjusted for adolescent's age (continuous: months), BMI (continuous: kg/m²), and creatinine (mg/dL), maternal schooling (primary/secondary/university) and intelligence, and for all metals simultaneously (categorised into tertiles).

Model 2: additionally, adjusted for passive tobacco smoking (yes/no) and total fish intake (<1 portion/month/>1 portion/month/>1 portion/week) of adolescents. sBDNF: serum BDNF; metBDNF: BDNF gene methylation. * $p < 0.05$; † $p < 0.10$. (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2022).

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This study was published in the International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, under the title “**Exploring the relationship between metal exposure, BDNF, and behavior in adolescent males**” (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2022).

4.3 Pilot study 3: Non-persistent pesticides metabolites and BDNF

Numerous contemporary, non-persistent pesticides present neurotoxicity concerns. Therefore, we aimed to investigate the relationship between exposure to various non-persistent pesticides, BDNF, and behavioural functioning in adolescents. Thus, concentrations of four organophosphate (OP) insecticide metabolites, including 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy), 2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxypyrimidine (IMPy), malathion diacid (MDA), and diethyl thiophosphate (DETP); two generic metabolites of pyrethroids, 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) and dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid (DCCA) the metabolite of insecticide carbaryl 1-naphthol (1-N); and the metabolite of ethylene-bis-dithiocarbamate fungicides ethylene thiourea (ETU), were measured in spot urine samples from adolescent males aged 15-17 years from the INMA cohort in Spain (where only boys were recruited). BDNF protein serum level and DNA methylation of the BDNF gene were measured and adolescents’ behaviour was reported by parents using the Child Behaviour Check List (CBCL/6-18). This pilot study 3 included 140 adolescents, of whom 118 had data on BDNF gene DNA methylation. Linear regression, weighted quantile sum (WQS) for mixture effects, and mediation models were fit.

IMPy, MDA, DCCA, and ETU were detected in more than 70% of urine samples, DETP in 53%, and TCPy, 3-PBA, and 1-N in less than 50% of samples. Higher levels of IMPy, TCPy, and ETU were significantly associated with more behavioural problems, including social, thought problems, and rule-breaking symptoms. IMPy, MDA, DETP, and 1-N were significantly associated with decreased serum BDNF levels, while MDA, 3-PBA, and ETU were associated with higher DNA methylation percentages at several CpGs. WQS models suggest a mixture effect on higher behavioural problems and BDNF DNA methylation at several CpGs. A mediated effect of serum BDNF within IMPy-thought and IMPy-rule breaking associations was observed.

BDNF biomarkers measured at different levels of biological organisation provided novel information regarding the potential disruption of behavioural function due to contemporary pesticides, highlighting exposure to diazinon (IMPy) and the combined effect of IMPy, MDA, DCCA and ETU concentrations. However, further research is warranted.

A draft article with these results is under review in Environment Research Journal (2022).

4.4 Comparison of BDNF and KISS-1 levels in maternal serum, cord serum and placenta

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and kisspeptin-1 (KISS-1) are also expressed in the human placenta and regulate placental development and foetal growth with implications for foetal and pregnancy health (Mayeur et al. 2010, Hu et al. 2019, Radovick et al. 2019, Kapustin et al. 2020, Dingsdale et al. 2021, Rosenfeld 2021). It is not known whether the levels of BDNF and KISS-1 in maternal serum correlate with those in the placenta and umbilical cord serum, respectively. A marker that early and reliably indicates changes in BDNF/KISS-1 expression in the placenta and/or altered levels in foetal serum, however, would be of great value.

The objective of MUW-WP14 partner was to investigate if maternal BDNF and KISS1 levels may serve as effect markers for developmental disorders, comparing BDNF and KISS-1 levels in maternal serum, cord serum and placenta samples from the same mother-child pair.

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Maternal serum, cord serum, and whole placenta tissue from 65 healthy term pregnancies (30 female, 35 male neonates) were collected between July 2019 and October 2021 in the General Hospital Vienna (Ethic Vote No. 1404/2015) to be analysed for BDNF (pro-BDNF and mature BDNF) and KISS-1 serum levels by ELISA (Table 19). BDNF and KISS-1 expression levels in whole placenta aliquots stabilised in RNAlater solution were analysed by qPCR. Data from medical records and questionnaires were used to identify potential confounders.

Table 19: Study group characteristics (N=65)

	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Maternal age (y)	34.6	5.5	22	45
Pre-pregnancy BMI	24.6	5.3	17	40
Pregnancy BMI	28.2	5.8	21	44
Gestational length (d)	270	7.2	249	288
Birth weight (g)	3297	442	2480	4830

Mature BDNF and proBDNF were quantified using the "Mature BDNF/proBDNF Combo Rapid ELISA Kit" (Biosensis, BEK-2240) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Human serum samples were diluted 1:10 for proBDNF and 1:50 for mature BDNF to be within the detection range of the ELISA assay (0-1000 pg/ml). Table 20 shows BDNF and KISS-1 levels in maternal serum (MatS) and cord serum (CordS) from 66 healthy delivery mothers. The concentrations of the reference material for pro-BDNF (463 ± 14.7) as well as for mature-BDNF (262 ± 7.5) were well within the certified range (pro-BDNF: 350-650; mature-BDNF: 175-325). BDNF levels were higher in maternal serum than in cord serum, whereas the opposite was the case for KISS-1 serum levels (Table 20, Figure 22).

KISS-1 was quantified by "KISS-1 Metastasis Suppressor (KISS-1) ELISA Kit" (antibodies-online, ABIN6962789) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Human serum samples were diluted 1:10 to be within the detection range of the KISS-1 ELISA assay (0-1000 pg/ml). KISS-1 serum levels were lower in maternal serum than in cord serum (Table 20, Figure. 22).

Table 20: Descriptive statistics of BDNF and KISS-1 levels in maternal serum (MatS) and cord serum (CordS) (n=65, respectively)

	MatS-proBDNF (pg/ml)	CordS-proBDNF (pg/ml)	MatS-matureBDNF (pg/ml)	CordS-mature BDNF (pg/ml)	MatS-KISS-1 (pg/ml)	CordS-KISS-1 (pg/ml)
Mean	53 639	46 821	17 610	15 994	12 733	19 682
SD	12 167	12 934	4 142	4 334	5 682	8 249
MIN	29 600	23 921	10 027	9 508	4 014	6 444
MAX	79 538	78 975	26 578	26 385	26 859	38 359
25th Perc.	44 303	37 525	14 136	11 969	8 113	13 019
50th Perc.	52 571	44 411	18 094	15 702	12 539	18 419
75th Perc.	65 069	56 355	20 503	19 393	15 864	26 366

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Maternal and cord serum levels were significantly positively correlated (pro-BDNF: $r=0.58$, mature-BDNF: $r=0.52$, KISS-1: $r=0.68$, $p<0.05$ each), indicating that maternal serum levels reflect cord serum levels to a sufficient and promising extent. It will be of great interest to determine whether placental expression of BDNF and KISS-1 is also related to serum levels.

Figure 22: BDNF and KISS-1 concentrations in maternal serum differ from cord serum concentrations (Student's t-Test * $P<0.05$, ** $P<0.01$, *** $P<0.001$)

4.5 Potential new effect biomarkers associated with acrylamide exposure in the EuroMix cohort

There is a general exposure of humans to acrylamide (AA) due to its formation in carbohydrate-rich foods during heat treatment. AA is classified as a probable human carcinogen (Group 2A) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). EFSA (EFSA 2015) has also expressed a concern for cancer risk. AA is also a recognised human neurotoxicant, but there is a scarcity of data on potential subtle effects of AA background exposure on brain function in humans.

Further, no epidemiological study has so far addressed neurodevelopmental effects associated with AA exposure in early life, but animal experiments give rise to concern (Lindeman et al. 2021). Although occupational data clearly show neurological deficits after exposure to higher levels of AA through inhalation and skin, there is a knowledge gap on the relation between AA in food items and possible neurological effects especially during early development, but also in adults.

The **main objective** was to explore the application of plasma proteomic profiling for the identification of novel candidate biomarkers of neurologic effect, as a proof of concept within HBM4EU. For this purpose, NIPH has implemented the Olink neurological panel (www.Olink.com) in the EuroMix human biomonitoring study population (Husoy et al. 2019) as an explorative study to ponder whether these biomarker screening panels are useful tools to define targeted set of protein biomarkers that can be used in the aligned studies as well as in European epidemiological studies.

Study population

The EuroMix human biomonitoring study was established at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) and was part of the EU funded project EuroMix "European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures". The study has been described in detail by Husøy and co-workers (Husoy et al. 2019). The study population of the EuroMix human biomonitoring study comprises 144 healthy adults. It was designed to give an in-depth knowledge about human

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external and internal exposures to environmental chemicals in food and in personal care products. Questionnaire data combined with measurements of pollutants or their metabolites in blood/serum and urine (24 h urine samples) are available. However, there are no health outcomes available except BMI, allergy, and asthma.

In short, participants were recruited among healthy employees from governmental institutes and authorities, and from universities in the counties of Oslo and Akershus in Norway between September 2016 and November 2017. The study recruited 144 participants (44 males aged 25–72 years and 100 females aged 24–72 years). The participant's reported their age, weight, height, education and smoking habits in questionnaires, as well as their consumption of foods and drinks in a semi-quantitative food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) as well as weighed food diaries. After the collection of the data and biological samples, the ID key was destroyed to fully anonymise this data. The study was approved by the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REK ID no 2015/1868) and all the participants provided their written informed consent. A total of 140 participants had complete information on blood and urinary exposure biomarkers as well as plasma biomarkers of effect. Measurement of the neurology-related biomarkers was co-funded by HBM4EU.

AA and GA analysis

Measurements of the mercapturic acid metabolites of acrylamide (AAMA, GAMA) in urine were performed autumn 2020 by Admescope (Södertelje, Sweden) as a part of the EuroMix project. The metabolites were analysed using a solid phase extraction (SPE) followed by LC-MS/MS. Acrylamide adducts of haemoglobin (Hb) were measured in the blood of EuroMix participants by Stockholm University spring 2021, as a part of the EuroMix project. The adducts were measured using LC-MS using the so-called FIRE procedure.

Proteomic analysis

Olink (www.Olink.com) has developed the Proseek Multiplex biomarker panels. The Olink® Target 96 panels allow for the simultaneous measurement of 92 proteins using a very small volume of plasma by real-time PCR using the Fluidigm BioMark HD real-time PCR platform and the Proximity Extension Assay (PEA) technology. Plasma samples representing 141 of the 144 EuroMix participants were sent to Olink for proteomics analysis of protein biomarkers using the Olink target 96 neurology panel (<https://www.olink.com/application/olink-for-neurology-studies/>). Details regarding limits of quantification (LOQ), reproducibility and validations are given at Olink webpage (<https://www.olink.com/content/uploads/2021/09/olink-neurology-validation-data-v2.1.pdf>). Markers with < 80% values above LOD were excluded from further analyses. Values below detection limit (LOD) were replaced by $LOD/\sqrt{2}$. In total, 88 proteins from 140 individuals were analysed.

Statistical analysis

To test whether differences in AA exposure were associated with changes in neuro-proteomic profiles, NIPH partners performed association studies between the measured quantity of AAMA and GAMA in urine and AA-Hb adducts with the quantitative measurements of targeted protein using 'Olink' technology.

Personal data such as sex, age, smoking habits, education, and body-mass-index (BMI) were available and used in the analyses to adjust for known covariates. Data were inspected for any missing values and those were imputed using average values, separately for females and males. Distributions of variables prior statistics were also checked. Log transformations were performed for numeric variables: AAMA, GAMA, BMI and AA-Hb-adduct to ensure normal distribution. Other

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Table 21: Means levels with associated statistics of urinary acrylamide (AAMA) and glycidamide (GAMA), and blood acrylamide (AA-Hb-adducts)

Exposure biomarker	Mean	SD	1 st quartile	3 rd quartile	Min	Max
AAMA (ug)	152.8	99.8	86.45	189.9	23	679
GAMA (ug)	12.1	9.2	5.5	15.6	0.4	50.6
AA-Hb-adducts (pmol/g Hb)	35.6	16.1	25.2	40.9	13.1	125.5

Associations between markers of AA exposure and the neurology markers:

Proteins with significant associations ($p < 0.05$) with AAMA when adjusted for smoking habits, BMI, education status, sex and age were the following: CNTN5 ($p = 0.0007$, Figure 24), TMPRSS5 ($p = 0.022$), and PVR ($p = 0.055$). PVR was additionally significant for sex ($p = 0.023$) while CNTN5 was significant for BMI ($p = 0.0086$) and age ($p < 0.0001$). None of these proteins were significant after applying Lasso procedure with AIC, suggesting that found associations are plausible but weak.

Figure 24: Leverage Plot for CNTN5

There were 3 weak significant associations found for the GAMA exposure variable: TNFRSF12A ($p = 0.029$), CLEC10A ($p = 0.034$), and Siglec-9 ($p = 0.016$). None of these proteins were significant after applying Lasso procedure with AIC, suggesting that found associations are plausible but weak.

There were more signal from AA-Hg-adduct compared to the urinary markers. NIPH found 21 associations between AA-Hg-adduct levels and following proteins: JAM-B ($p = 0.0051$; Figure 25), CADM3 ($p = 0.0061$), TMPRSS5 ($p = 0.01$), BMP-4 ($p = 0.013$), CDH3 ($p = 0.015$), CLEC10A ($p = 0.015$), CNTN5 ($p = 0.016$; Figure 26), GDF-8 ($p = 0.02$), NTRK3 ($p = 0.02$), EPHB6 ($p = 0.023$), TNFRSF21 ($p = 0.023$), UNC5C ($p = 0.024$), NEP ($p = 0.0256$), LAYN ($p = 0.026$), GDNFR-alpha-3 ($p = 0.026$), VWC2 ($p = 0.034$), ROBO2 ($p = 0.037$), ADAM22 ($p = 0.037$), N-CDase ($p = 0.040$), SCARF2 ($p = 0.047$), Dkk-4 ($p = 0.049$).

Additional analysis with LASSO with AIC criterion used, revealed that 4 biomarkers survived this procedure: JAM-B, CNTN5, CLEC10A and EPHB6.

Figure 25: Leverage plot for JAM-B protein

Figure 26: Leverage Plot for CNTN5

A neuronal network was trained to predict the outcome of the numeric variables AAMA, GAMA and AA-Hb-adduct, respectively. Although the neuronal network reached the convergence, the level of the biomarkers was difficult to predict by given parameters (Figure 27). This was already reflected in the training data.

Figure 27: Actual by Predicted Plot for top) AA-Hb-adduct middle) AAMA, bottom GAMA. Training data (left), Validation data (right)

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Associations between markers of AA exposure and the inflammation markers:

Within the EuroMix project, NIPH has also data for the Olink target 92 inflammation panel. In short, they found weaker associations between the inflammation markers and the AA exposure markers than for the neurology markers. The significant associations after adjustment were:

No significant associations were recorded for AAMA or GAMA. *AA-Hb-adducts*: MMP-10 ($p=0.024$), TGF- α ($p=0.026$), MCP-2 ($p=0.028$), Flt3L ($p=0.033$), IL-17C ($p=0.039$), IL7 ($p=0.048$) and ADA ($p=0.047$). None of these associations were significant after applying Lasso procedure with AIC.

Conclusions

Screening for potential protein biomarkers of effect in human plasma can be a valuable addition to metabolomic and transcriptomic data for the strengthening of causality and mode of action analysis in epidemiological studies. A high number of markers, from 48 to more than 3000 can be detected simultaneously using only a low volume of plasma or serum using Olink technology allowing for both (semi-)targeted and non-targeted approaches. Promising markers, or groups of markers, can subsequently be integrated into epidemiological studies linking exposures to health effects.

In our studies we have used a semi-targeted approach, looking specifically into the panel that was created for neurology (Olink Target 96). With this study we have identified a few potential biomarkers of effect associated with AA exposure.

However, in order to get enough power, a higher number of individuals should be analysed, or individuals should be selected from a high vs a low exposure group. None of the associations were significant after correction for multiple testing but four proteins, JAM-B, CNTN5, CLEC10A and EPHB6, were significantly associated with AA-Hb-adducts following a Lasso procedure. These proteins are candidates for inclusion in larger cohort studies. The associations with the AA-Hg-adducts were more numerous compared to those for the urinary AA exposure biomarkers. AA-Hb-adducts accumulate over the lifespan of the erythrocyte and thus represent the AA exposure during a period of up to 120 days whereas AAMA and GAMA urinary metabolites represents short time exposures.

4.6 Adiponectin & Leptin: fine-tuning, precision and accuracy

UGR team has developed the appropriated methodology to measure two metabolic markers, adiponectin and leptin, in human serum samples for their implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Quality Control (QC) and Pilot Study for Adiponectin

According to the designed quality control, each serum sample was tested in duplicate on two different plates. Initially, different dilutions (1:150, 1:300 and 1:600) were performed, although the 1:300 dilution was the condition proposed by the manufacturer. We started with an initial volume of 5 μ L to measure these metabolic markers and proceeded through different steps to achieve the established dilutions.

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Sample preparation

Each sample was evaluated in duplicate at different dilutions with a final volume of 300 μ L, as shown in Figure 28.

1. Dilution A (10x): 5 μ L of serum sample + 45 μ L of Dilution Buffer
2. Dilution B:
 - **15x (Dilution 1:150)**: 20 μ L of Dilution A + 280 μ L of Dilution Buffer
 - **30x (Dilution 1:300)**: 10 μ L of Dilution A + 290 μ L of Dilution Buffer
 - **60x (Dilution 1:600)**: 5 μ L of Dilution A + 295 μ L of Dilution Buffer

Figure 28: Procedure followed for samples dilutions

Reagents preparation for ELISA kit procedure

- Dilution Buffer (1x): Dilution Buffer Concentrate (10x) should be diluted 10-fold with distilled water before using (20 mL of Dilution Buffer Concentrate (10x) with 180 mL of distilled water).
- Wash Solution (1x): Wash Solution Concentrate (10x) should be diluted 10-fold with distilled water before using (100 ml of Wash Solution Concentrate (10x) with 900 mL of distilled water).
- Quality Control (HIGH and LOW) (300x): Quality controls (30x) should be diluted 10-fold with the Dilution Buffer before using (30 μ L of QC with 270 μ L of Dilution Buffer)

Assembly of the adiponectin microplate

Standards, ready-to-use, blank and samples are added in the wells according to the quality control design, which is briefly explained below: Rows 1 and 2 are designed for standards, while rows 3 to 12 are designed for analysed samples. Specifically, diluted samples are loaded on rows 3 to 10 of plate 1 and their duplicates on plate 2, in order to calculate the inter-assay coefficient of variability (CV). To obtain the intra-assay CV, the duplicates of raw sample 11 are loaded into raw sample 12, as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Quality control designed to measure adiponectin in serum samples

Adiponectin levels were measured with an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using an Adiponectin (human), ELISA kit ALX-850-377 (ENZO Life Science, Farmingdale, NY). Serum samples were selected from boys (n=25) belonging to the Spanish INMA-Granada birth cohort. During the last follow up visit (2017-2019) of the INMA-Granada, 155 males adolescents at the age 15-17 years agreed to participate and underwent both physical and psychological examination at the San Cecilio University Hospital (Granada, Spain). Whole venous blood was collected from participants (n=134) at 5-7pm, processed and stored at -80°C until analysis (Castiello et al., 2020). Only 25 serum samples were defrosted, vortexed, diluted (1:150, 1:300 and 1:600) and tested according to manufacturer’s instructions at the Centre of Biomedical Research (CIBM) of the University of Granada (Spain), as it can be seen at the Figure 30.

Figure 30: Quality control designed for serum adiponectin levels

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ELISA kit procedure was carried out as describe below:

1. Add 100µl of Standards, Blank (Dilution Buffer quality controls (high and low) and diluted human serum samples into the appropriate wells.
2. Incubate the plate at room temperature (25°C) for 1 hour, shaking at 300 rpm on an orbital microplate shaker.
3. Wash the wells 3-times with Wash Solution (0.35 mL/well). After final wash, invert and tap the plate strongly against paper towel.
4. Add 100µl of Conjugate Solution into each well.
5. Incubate the plate at room temperature (25°C) for 1 hour, shaking at 300 rpm on an orbital microplate shaker.
6. Wash the wells 3-times with Wash Solution (0.35 ml/well). After final wash, invert and tap the plate strongly against paper towel.
7. Add 100µl of Substrate Solution into each well. Avoid exposing the microtiter plate to direct sunlight. Covering the plate with aluminium foil.
8. Incubate the plate for 10 minutes at room temperature (20-30°C). The incubation time may be extended [up to 20 minutes for serum and plasma samples] if the reaction temperature is below than 20°C. Do not shake the plate during the incubation.
9. Stop the colour development by adding 100µl of Stop Solution.
10. Determine the absorbance of each well using a microplate reader set to 450nm, preferably with the reference wavelength set to 630nm (acceptable range: 550 - 650nm). Subtract readings at 630nm (550 - 650nm) from the readings at 450nm. The absorbance should be read within 5 minutes following step 9.

Results

The assay procedure was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. In total, 25 serum samples from the INMA-Granada Cohort were analysed in duplicate and the mean value was calculated to obtain the level of adiponectin present in each serum sample. The data obtained indicate that the 1:300 dilution is the most suitable for measuring adiponectin levels in the serum samples, as suggested by the manufacturer's protocol, since the optical density obtained (450-620 nm) in all the samples analysed was within the linearity of the standard curve for this dilution.

The intra- and inter-assay coefficients of variability were 3.60% and 7.13%, respectively, both within the quality range established by the manufacturer, < 5% for intra-assay and < 15% for inter-assay. Furthermore, the concentration obtained in the quality controls (high and low) was similar to that established by the manufacturer (18.3 and 7.43 µg/mL), 16.89 and 8.34 µg/mL, respectively.

Figure 31 shows the distribution of adiponectin levels obtained in the serum samples selected from the INMA-Granada Cohort. In addition, Table 22 shows the final adiponectin concentration (µg/mL) in the serum samples analysed using the ELISA kit supplied by ENZO. In summary, serum adiponectin levels ranged from 9 µg/mL to 21.51 µg/mL, with a mean and geometric value of 13.54 and 13.15 µg/mL, respectively. The distribution of total serum adiponectin concentrations was as follows: P25th = 11.49 µg/mL, P50th= 12.99 µg/mL and P75th= 15.82 µg/mL.

Figure 31: Distribution of serum adiponectin concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) among teenagers from the INMA-Granada Cohort (n=25)

Table 22: Absorbance & adiponectin concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in serum samples (Elisa-ENZO kit)

SAMPLE	Absorbance			Concentration		
	OD (450-620 nm)		Mean \pm SD	$\mu\text{g/ml}$		Mean \pm SD
1	2.237	2.626	2.432 \pm 0.275	11.674	14.298	12.986 \pm 1.855
2	2.022	2.386	2.204 \pm 0.257	10.341	12.639	11.490 \pm 1.625
3	3.109	3.469	3.289 \pm 0.254	18.113	21.633	19.873 \pm 2.489
4	2.503	2.627	2.565 \pm 0.088	13.434	14.306	13.870 \pm 0.617
5	2.034	2.195	2.114 \pm 0.114	10.412	11.404	10.908 \pm 0.701
6	2.750	2.665	2.708 \pm 0.06	15.208	14.584	14.896 \pm 0.441
7	2.646	3.108	2.877 \pm 0.327	14.442	18.104	16.273 \pm 2.59
8	3.382	3.529	3.456 \pm 0.104	20.704	22.323	21.514 \pm 1.145
9	2.334	2.326	2.330 \pm 0.005	12.299	12.250	12.274 \pm 0.035
10	2.748	2.909	2.829 \pm 0.114	15.193	16.441	15.817 \pm 0.882
11	1.763	1.869	1.816 \pm 0.075	8.820	9.432	9.126 \pm 0.432
12	2.221	2.441	2.331 \pm 0.156	11.568	13.009	12.288 \pm 1.018
13	1.765	1.823	1.794 \pm 0.041	8.836	9.167	9.001 \pm 0.234
14	2.063	2.474	2.268 \pm 0.291	10.587	13.233	11.910 \pm 1.871
15	2.151	2.273	2.212 \pm 0.086	11.131	11.905	11.518 \pm 0.547
16	3.043	3.161	3.102 \pm 0.083	17.543	18.572	18.058 \pm 0.728
17	2.461	2.559	2.510 \pm 0.069	13.146	13.823	13.484 \pm 0.479
18	2.493	2.541	2.517 \pm 0.034	13.367	13.699	13.533 \pm 0.235
19	2.286	2.320	2.303 \pm 0.024	11.985	12.205	12.095 \pm 0.156
20	1.851	1.954	1.902 \pm 0.073	9.327	9.933	9.630 \pm 0.429
21	2.877	2.884	2.881 \pm 0.005	16.184	16.243	16.214 \pm 0.042

SAMPLE	Absorbance			Concentration		
	OD (450-620 nm)		Mean ± SD	µg/ml		Mean ± SD
22	2.616	2.598	2.607 ± 0.013	14.228	14.097	14.162 ± 0.092
23	3.144	3.186	3.165 ± 0.03	18.425	18.803	18.614 ± 0.267
24	1.972	1.932	1.952 ± 0.028	10.040	9.805	9.922 ± 0.166
25	1.565	2.058	1.811 ± 0.349	7.719	10.558	9.138 ± 2.008

Quality Control (QC) and Pilot Study: Leptin

According to the quality control designed, each serum sample was analysed in duplicate using two different plates. Initially, different dilutions were performed (1:10, 1:20 and 1:50), with the 1:20 dilution being the condition proposed by the manufacturer. The initial volume to measure this metabolic marker was different depending on the dilution selected.

Sample preparation

Each sample was assessed in duplicate at different dilutions with a 220 µL as a final volume, as indicated below and in the Figure 32.

- **Dilution (1:10):** 22 µL of serum sample + 198 µL of Assay Buffer 17
- **Dilution (1:20):** 11 µL of serum sample + 209 µL of Assay Buffer 17
- **Dilution (1:50):** 4.4 µL of serum sample + 215.6 µL of Assay Buffer 17

Figure 32: Procedure followed for samples dilutions

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Reagents preparation for ELISA kit procedure

- Wash Buffer (1x): Wash Buffer Concentrate (20x) should be diluted 20-fold with distilled water before using (50 ml of Wash Buffer Concentrate (20x) with 950 mL of deionised water).
- Leptin Standard Curve: The standard curve is prepared with seven points of calibration (Figure 33):

Stock solution (2000 pg/ml) = powder + 1 ml Assay Diluent 17 (sit at room temperature for 5 minutes): Std. 1

- Std. 2 (1000 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Stock/Std.1 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17
- Std. 3 (500 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Std.2 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17
- Std. 4 (250 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Std.3 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17
- Std. 5 (125 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Std.4 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17
- Std. 6 (62.5 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Std.5 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17
- Std. 7 (31.25 pg/ml) = 500 μ L Std.6 + 500 μ L Assay Diluent B 17

Zero Std. (0 pg/ml) o Blank = 300 uL Assay Biluent 17

Figure 33: Standard Curve preparation

Assembly of the leptin microplate

Standards, ready-to-use, blank and samples are added in the wells according to the quality control design, which is briefly explained below: Rows 1 and 2 are designed for standards, while rows 3 to 12 are designed for analysed samples.

Specifically, diluted samples are loaded on rows 3 to 10 of plate 1 and their duplicates on plate 2, in order to calculate the inter-assay coefficient of variability (CV). To obtain the intra-assay CV, the duplicates of raw sample 11 are loaded into raw sample 12, as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Quality control designed to measure leptin in serum samples

Leptin levels were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using the leptin ELISA kit (human), ADI-900-028A (ENZO Life Science, Farmingdale, NY). Serum samples were selected from adolescent males (n=26) belonging to the Spanish INMA-Granada birth cohort. During the last follow-up visit (2017-2019) of INMA-Granada, 155 male adolescents aged 15-17 years agreed to participate and underwent a physical and psychological examination at the Hospital Universitario San Cecilio (Granada, Spain).

Venous whole blood was collected from participants (n=134) at 5-7 pm, processed and stored at -80°C until analysis (Castiello et al., 2020). Only 26 serum samples were thawed, vortex-mixed, diluted (1:10, 1:20 and 1:50) and analysed according to the manufacturer's instructions at the Centro de Investigación Biomédica (CIBM) of the University of Granada (Spain), as can be seen in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Quality control designed for serum leptin levels

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ELISA kit procedure was carried out as describe below:

1. Add 100µl of Blank (Assay Buffer 17), standards and samples of the appropriate wells.
2. Seal the plate and incubate for 1 hour without shaking at room temperature.
3. Empty the contents of the wells and wash by adding 400µl/well of wash buffer. Repeat 3 more times for a total of 4 washes. After the final wash, empty or aspirate the wells and firmly tap the plate on a lint free paper towel to remove any remaining wash buffer.
4. Add 100µl of yellow antibody into each well except the blank.
5. Seal the plate and incubate for 1 hour without shaking at room temperature.
6. Wash as above (Step 3).
7. Add 100µl of blue conjugate to each well except the blank.
8. Seal the plate and incubate for 30 minutes without shaking at room temperature.
9. Wash as above (Step 3).
10. Add 100µl of substrate solution into each well.
11. Seal the plate and incubate for 30 minutes without shaking at room temperature.
12. Add 100µl of stop solution into each well.
13. After blanking the plate reader against the substrate only blank, read optical density at 450nm. If plate reader is not capable of adjusting for the blank, manually subtract the mean OD of the substrate blank from all readings.

Results

The assay procedure was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. In total, 25 serum samples from the INMA-Granada cohort were evaluated in duplicate and the mean value was calculated to obtain the level of leptin present in each serum sample analysed. The results obtained indicate that the 1:20 dilution is the most suitable dilution for measuring leptin levels in serum samples, as indicated in the manufacturer's protocol, since the optical density (450 nm) obtained for all selected samples was found to be within the linearity of the standard curve.

The intra- and inter-assay coefficients of variability were 3.92% and 6.63%, respectively, both quality parameters are within the manufacturer's guidelines, < 5% for intra-assay and < 15% for inter-assay.

Figure 36 shows the distribution of leptin levels in the selected serum samples from the INMA-Granada Cohort. In addition, table 23 shows the final adiponectin concentration (ng/ml) in the serum samples analysed by the ELISA kit supplied by ENZO. In summary, serum leptin levels ranged from 1.42 ng/mL to 35.54 ng/mL, and the mean and geometric mean were 8.07 and 4.66 ng/mL, respectively. The distribution of total serum adiponectin concentrations was as follows P25th = 2.11 ng/mL, P50th= 2.99 ng/mL and P75th= 10.98 ng/mL.

Figure 36: Distribution of serum leptin concentrations (ng/mL) among teenagers from the INMA-Granada Cohort (n=26)

Table 23: Absorbance & Leptin concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in serum samples (Elisa-ENZO kit)

SAMPLE	Absorbance			Concentration		
	OD (450 nm)		Mean \pm SD	ng/ml		Mean \pm SD
1	0.075	0.076	0.075 \pm 0.001	1.907	1.732	1.820 \pm 0.123
2	0.112	0.129	0.121 \pm 0.012	2.421	2.294	2.357 \pm 0.090
3	0.166	0.128	0.147 \pm 0.027	3.163	2.278	2.720 \pm 0.626
4	0.106	0.133	0.120 \pm 0.019	2.338	2.339	2.338 \pm 0.000
5	0.324	0.403	0.363 \pm 0.055	5.298	5.144	5.221 \pm 0.109
6	0.047	0.037	0.042 \pm 0.007	1.515	1.332	1.423 \pm 0.130
7	0.412	0.442	0.427 \pm 0.021	6.457	5.555	6.006 \pm 0.638
8	1.072	1.276	1.174 \pm 0.144	14.645	14.108	14.377 \pm 0.380
9	3.184	3.323	3.254 \pm 0.099	36.716	34.370	35.543 \pm 1.658
10	0.094	0.092	0.093 \pm 0.001	2.171	1.907	2.039 \pm 0.186
11	0.250	0.246	0.248 \pm 0.003	4.303	3.518	3.911 \pm 0.555
12	0.118	0.142	0.130 \pm 0.017	2.502	2.424	2.463 \pm 0.055
13	0.118	0.130	0.124 \pm 0.008	2.504	2.301	2.402 \pm 0.143
14	0.483	0.549	0.516 \pm 0.047	7.374	6.663	7.019 \pm 0.503
15	0.363	0.393	0.378 \pm 0.022	5.808	5.048	5.428 \pm 0.537
16	1.592	1.967	1.780 \pm 0.265	20.583	21.064	20.823 \pm 0.340
17	2.254	2.680	2.467 \pm 0.301	27.618	28.110	27.864 \pm 0.348
18	0.941	1.021	0.981 \pm 0.057	13.085	11.517	12.301 \pm 1.109
19	0.053	0.057	0.055 \pm 0.003	1.602	1.537	1.570 \pm 0.045
20	1.172	1.337	1.255 \pm 0.117	15.817	14.733	15.275 \pm 0.767
21	0.128	0.151	0.139 \pm 0.017	2.636	2.523	2.579 \pm 0.080
22	0.182	0.163	0.173 \pm 0.013	3.383	3.129	3.256 \pm 0.180

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SAMPLE	Absorbance			Concentration		
	OD (450 nm)		Mean ± SD	ng/ml		Mean ± SD
23	2.155	1.967	2.061 ± 0.133	26.593	24.626	25.609 ± 1.391
24	0.054	0.051	0.053 ± 0.002	1.618	1.579	1.599 ± 0.028
25	0.094	0.102	0.098 ± 0.006	1.921	2.010	1.965 ± 0.063
26	0.088	0.086	0.087 ± 0.001	1.862	1.844	1.853 ± 0.013

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5 Future steps

After the laboratory analysis of all effect biomarkers, the next step will be to assess their AOPs with the selected substances of the first priority set. Therefore, statistical methods are defined per type of research question.

In this regard, for those aligned studies that have measured/obtained specific effect markers and health effects statistical analysis could be performed to look into the path analysis linking exposure to health effects via established effect biomarkers (linked to WP13 and WP14). The following path analyses will be investigated:

- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to neurodevelopment in children, with molecular and clinical markers as BDNF (UGR, INSERM, EPIUD)

- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to BMI & metabolism in children, with available clinical markers as cholesterol, triglycerides (NIPH)

- Phthalates/DINCH in relation to BMI & metabolism in teenagers, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (NIPH, UGR, MU, INSERM)
- PFASs in relation to BMI & metabolism in teenagers, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (KI, UGR, MU, INSERM)

- Phthalates/DINCH and PFASs in relation to sexual maturation in teenagers, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (VITO, UGR, INSERM, MU)

From these statistical analyses results, scientific peer-reviewed publications and policy briefs will be initiated (in collaboration with WP2 and WP5), but this work will probably not be finalised by the end of 2021.

With the results of the implementation of classical and novel biomarkers of effect, several scientific publications are also being preparing.

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6 Conclusions

Several European cohorts participating in the HBM4EU aligned studies have provided biological samples and preliminary results on biomarkers of effect are shown in this first report on the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised substances in the aligned studies.

Although it is not yet possible to draw conclusions, the data indicate that the implementation of biomarkers of effect together with information on exposure levels in HBM studies could help epidemiological research to establish convincing causal relationships, and contribute to understand, resolve and answer some important policy questions. In this regard, for those aligned studies that have assessed exposure to specific compounds prioritised in HBM4EU, measured selected effect markers and have health effect information available, specific statistical analyses are being performed in relation to the established causal relationships exposure-health effects.

The inclusion of biomarkers of effect may also help to understand the biological mechanisms through which exposure is related to adverse health effects.

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